

T Mon (P 27.027d) $p=1.270$ $d=1503.4\text{pc}$ $E(B-V)=0.235$; $IR_{ex} = 0.188 \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{2.247(1.2-\lambda)}} - 0.5 \right)$

